

The Influence of Quality Work Life and Job Insecurity on Performance with Social Support as a Moderating Variable in MSMEs in Gianyar Regency

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Abstract: The purpose of this research is to explain the role of social support in moderating the effect of quality of work life and job insecurity. This research was conducted on SMEs in the weaving craft industry in Gianyar district with a sample of 115 respondents through purposive sampling. Collection techniques using interviews and questionnaires. Data were analyzed by Moderating Regression Analysis. The results showed that quality of work life has a positive and significant effect on the performance of MSME employees, job insecurity has a negative and significant effect on MSME employee performance, social support moderates the effect of quality of work life on MSME employee performance, and social support moderates the effect of job insecurity on employee performance. MSMEs. The implication of this research is that it can contribute ideas for SMEs. The contribution of thought in question is that MSMEs always develop the results of this research in practice and can be a reference for other researchers who want to research Quality of Work Life, Job Insecurity, social support, and performance. Theoretically, this research also provides an understanding that Quality of Work Life, Job Insecurity, social support, and performance can actually provide benefits or value to businesses so that they can improve MSME performance.

Keywords: quality of work life, job insecurity, social support, employee performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) is one of the economic activities carried out by most Indonesian people. MSME management is currently undergoing changes where previously business actors did it manually, for example starting from payments, sales, even to managing MSME funds. The development of MSMEs must also be accompanied by the development of Human Resources (HR). Given the crucial role of SMEs as one of the pillars of the economy, UKM actors must be able to demonstrate quality both in terms of products and human resources. Even though the SME business is still relatively new and small, there is no reason not to neglect the quality and role of HR. The contribution of good human resources will have an impact on the success of the brand, the ability to compete and the sustainability of SMEs in the future. To build quality human resources and be able to contribute optimally, planned HR management steps are needed. HR development must be carried out not only for MSMEs as business owners but also for their workers (Rochmah, 2018).

The definition of performance in the context of management is a work performance or work results of a person based on the quantity and quality achieved in carrying out its functions in accordance with the responsibilities received. Good HR management will have an impact on improving employee performance and will have a direct effect on improving overall company performance. To achieve superior employee performance, companies need to understand and understand what motivates and needs employees in their work environment. Good performance is optimal performance, namely performance in accordance with organizational standards. Therefore the organization will maintain a conducive working atmosphere

which will create a good quality of work life for the achievement of organizational goals. Quality of Work Life is the right way to improve the quality of human resources in a company. By going through a process, human resources will maximize responsibility for their work (Aryansah and Erika, 2013) so that it will improve performance. Dilaningrum et al. (2017) stated that a high quality of work life can improve employee performance, so that the existence of a quality quality of work life in the organization will make employees have an obligation to contribute to the organization to achieve organizational goals.

An organization needs to pay attention to job insecurity because it also greatly affects performance. Job insecurity is a perception of loss of continuity in work which includes the existence of work being done at this time and the problems in it. There are two forms of job insecurity, namely quantitative job insecurity, namely worrying about losing the job itself, and job continuity in the future. While qualitative job insecurity refers to feelings of potential loss or threat in the quality of organizational positions, such as deteriorating working conditions, lack of career opportunities, and decreased pay (Hellgren et al., 1999). Job insecurity is indeed considered to be closely related to mental health (Menéndez-Espina et al., 2019). This is because job insecurity is one of the long-term stressors experienced by employees related to their work, which can lead to decreased performance. Anxiety or worry that is felt will certainly interfere with the implementation of work so to minimize this it is necessary to get positive support from the people around him. The encouragement given can be a spirit that creates psychological comfort and can finally work optimally.

Employees often need attention. Humans need the existence of other people to provide mutual assessment, help, support and cooperate in facing life's challenges. Individual group assistance to other individuals or other groups is called social support. Social support is more likely to be considered as an individual cognition that starts in terms of objective environmental symptoms and social support is an individual's perception of potential support or as perceived helpfulness and supportiveness. Social support is a form of care received from someone, in which there is good social relations, so that it is able to provide better changes (Darmasaputra & Satiningsih, 2013).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Performance

Performance or job performance is a measure used in comparing the acquisition of work results with the responsibilities given by the organization in a certain period of time to improve work performance (Siagian & Khair, 2018). Irmayanthi & Surya (2020) states that employee performance is not in the form of personal characteristics such as talent but in the form of abilities that have a real form or work that is achieved by employees when carrying out tasks received from related organizations or agencies. Performance is how an individual sets organizational goals, in the form of specific goals, namely individually or by demonstrating the right skills for the organization.

Quality of work life

Quality of work life is a broad understanding of safe and comfortable working conditions that enable employees to develop their potential at work (Chanana & Kumar Gupta, 2016). Irmayanthi & Surya (2020) state that quality of work life is defined as a concept in an organization that has the goal of improving the quality of life of employees in the organization.

Job Insecurity

Job insecurity is a condition of uncertainty about work, which causes an employee to become confused about his job in the circumstances he is currently living in (Triyono et al., 2020). Meanwhile, according to Mashudi et al. (2020) job insecurity is a feeling of insecurity and anxiety about work in the future.

Social Support

Social support is a form of care received from someone, in which there is good social relations, so that they are able to provide better changes (Achmad & Yuniawan, 2018). Meanwhile, according to Wulandari & Lestari (2018) social support is an encouragement that comes from the closest people who can provide psychological comfort

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The population of this study were SMEs in the weaving craft industry in Gianyar Regency. The sampling technique used in this study was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method, in which the sample was determined with certain considerations or criteria. The sample criteria in this study are as follows: Minimum education level is high school or equivalent, respondents who have worked for more than 5 years and are domiciled in Gianyar Regency, 115 respondents

who meet the criteria in this study. The analytical tools in this study are validity and reliability tests. Then the data analysis technique is Regression Moderating Analysis (RMA)

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

First of all, the Research Instrument Testing was carried out :

Reliability Test. The result of each Cronbach's Alpha value in each research instrument is greater than 0.6 (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6). These results indicate that all instruments are declared reliable, so they can be used to conduct research.

Validity test. Based on Table 4.3 it can be seen that all the correlation coefficients of the research variable indicators tested have a value greater than 0.30 ($r > 0.3$) and Sig < 0.05. These results indicate that all research indicators are declared valid.

Moderated Regression Analysis Results

In this study, the interaction test technique (Moderated Regression Analysis) was used, which is a special application of multiple linear regression. This study also examined the role of social support in moderating the effect of quality of work life and job insecurity on the performance of MSME actors in Gianyar Regency. In this study, the effect of quality of work life and job insecurity on performance was calculated through the SPSS 21.0 for windows program

Determination Analysis

Determination analysis was carried out to determine the extent to which the independent variables varied, namely quality of work life (X_1) and job insecurity (X_2), social support (M) on performance variables (Y). based on SPSS results the value of $R^2 = 56.9\%$, which means that 56.9% of the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency is influenced by the variables of quality of work life and job insecurity, and social support, and the remaining 43.1% is influenced by other variables which were not examined in this study.

Effect of Quality of Work Life on Performance

The hypothesis test shows that H1 is accepted, there is a significant positive effect of the Quality of Work Life variable on performance. If the Quality of Work Life is higher, the employee's performance will increase. The explanation of the results of this study is that employees who have a high Quality of Work Life tend to believe that work results depend on themselves and will show better performance. Employees who have a better Quality of Work Life will be more motivated to complete their jobs, resulting in satisfaction and will further improve their performance. For example, if employees want to get a bigger bonus or appreciation for their work, they must have a great desire to achieve it, by working as well as possible in accordance with the existing code of ethics.

Effect of Job Insecurity on Performance

The results of the hypothesis (H2) in this study indicate that Job Insecurity has a negative and significant effect on performance, in other words if Job Insecurity increases, the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will decrease. So the second hypothesis H2 is accepted. Job Insecurity is one of the factors that can affect employee performance.

The Role of Social Support in Moderating the Effect of Quality of Work Life on Performance

The results of the hypothesis (H3) in this study indicate that social support moderates the effect of Quality of Work Life on the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency. Where the resulting moderation effect is to strengthen relationships, in other words if there is social support, the positive influence of Quality of Work Life on the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will be further strengthened. Where social support is a pseudo moderator variable due to the coefficients b_2 and b_3 in the moderated regression analysis equation, namely the b_2 coefficient is stated to be significant and the b_3 coefficient is significant so that the third hypothesis is accepted. The role of social support in a company is not only directly related to performance. This is in line with research conducted by Iroegbu (2015) and Amalia (2020)

The Role of Social Support in Moderating the Effect of Job Insecurity on Performance

The results of the hypothesis (H4) in this study indicate that social support moderates the effect of Job Insecurity on the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency. Where the resulting moderating effect is to weaken the relationship, in other words if there is social support, the negative effect of Job Insecurity on the performance

of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will be further weakened. Where social support is a pseudo moderator variable due to the coefficients b_2 and b_3 in the moderated regression analysis equation, namely the b_2 coefficient is stated to be significant and the b_3 coefficient is significant so that the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the study, the conclusions related to the influence of Quality of Work Life, Job Insecurity, social support and on the Performance of UMKM Employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency are as follows:

- 1) Quality of work life has a positive and significant effect on performance, in other words, if the quality of work life increases, the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will increase
- 2) Job Insecurity has a negative and significant effect on performance, in other words, if Job Insecurity increases, the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will decrease.
- 3) Social support moderates the effect of Quality of Work Life on the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency. Where the resulting moderation effect is to strengthen relationships, in other words if there is a social support variable, the effect of Quality of Work Life on the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will be further strengthened
- 4) Social support moderates the effect of Job Insecurity on the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency. Where the resulting moderating effect is to weaken the relationship, in other words if there is a social support variable, the effect of Job Insecurity on the performance of UMKM employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will be further strengthened

Based on the description of the conclusions above, the suggestions that can be considered related to the influence of Quality of Work Life, Job Insecurity, social support and on the Performance of MSME Employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency are as follows:

- 1) MSME actors are expected to be able to improve the quality of work of employees through open communication, provide rewards according to employee performance, provide employee job security, and involve employees in the decision-making process
- 2) MSME actors are expected to pay more attention to the work environment faced by employees in order to minimize job insecurity felt by employees. Unfavorable work environment conditions can increase job insecurity and affect individual behavior at work
- 3) MSME actors are expected to provide more social support to employees so that employees are enthusiastic about working so that they can improve the progress of MSME weaving industry. Social support can be done by giving praise to employees who work hard, listening to employees' stories or complaints about workers and finding solutions to these problems
- 4) MSME actors are expected to pay more attention to the working relationship between employees where the employee's working relationship must always be in good condition so that they can still work together, if there is a conflict between employees, MSME actors must act as a neutral intermediary and help these employees resolve their problems

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